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Chemical Examination of *Lantana camara* Linn.

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LANTANA CAMARA Linn (N.O. Verbenaceae) causes severe photosensitisation during fruiting and flowering stages¹ and icterus in sheep. The leaves of the plant were extensively examined and isolated the triterpenes lantadene A, lantadene B^{2,3,4}, lantalic acid, lactic acid and 3-Keto ursolic acid⁵⁻⁸ and an unidentified ketosteroid lancamarone⁹.

In the present investigation the roots of the plant were examined. The root powder was extracted with hot EtOH and the extract on removal of the solvent gave a dark greenish brown residue (3%). The residue was fractionated into Et₂O (2%) and H₂O (1%) solubles. (The aqueous extract gave yellow colour with alkali and blue colour with acid). The Et₂O extract was fractionated into neutral (0.1% waxes) and acidic (1.9%) fractions by extraction with 5% NaOH. TLC on silica gel G indicated that the acid is a mixture of three or four compounds. One was separated and purified by fractional crystallisation from EtOH and chromatography over silica gel and identified as oleanolic acid (1.5%) C, 98.72; H, 10.81. C₃₀H₄₈O₃ requires C, 98.95 and H, 10.53%. (C, 1.2 in CHCl₃): m.p. 290°-92°: [α]_D+80°, I.R. 1665 cm⁻¹, 825 cm⁻¹: NMR spectra multiplet centered at 4.7τ (IH) for trisubstituted double bond: Prominent MS: right-half ratio Diels-Alder fragment m/e 248, m/e 233 (248-CH₃) and m/e 189 (233-CO₂): comparison of the acetate with authentic oleanolic acid acetate (m.m.p. and IR)].

The separation of the other compounds could not be effected as their R values are very close. The efforts for the separation and characterisation of the other triterpenes are in progress.

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Synthesis of 3,5-Dimethyl-1-naphthol*

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THE preparation of 3,5-dimethyl-1-naphthol from *o*-xylene after suitable modification of the sequence of reactions shown in Fig. 1 and reported earlier by Royals and Green² for the synthesis of 3,5-dimethyl-1-tetralone is described.

Experimental

*Diethyl (o-xyllyl) malonate*¹ (II): α -Bromo-*o*-xylene³ (I) (23.0 g; 0.12 M), b.p. 102°/15 mm; n_D^{30} 1.5746, obtained from *o*-xylene using N-bromosuccinimide as the brominating agent³ was treated with sodium

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